

SSTRESED: Scalable Semantic Trajectory Extraction for Simple Event Detection over Streaming Movement Data

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Abstract

We describe SSTRESED, a prototype focused on the real-time, online detection of simple, durative events over streaming movement data. It is the first prototype that establishes a direct connection between semantic trajectory extraction and simple event detection. SSTRESED is highly scalable by incorporating parallel processing in two separate, but connected, training and event detection pipelines implemented on state-of-the-art platforms, directly deployable in cloud environments.

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1 Introduction & Motivation

Detecting Simple, Derived Events (SDEs) is the first step towards Complex Event Recognition (CER) [3, 4, 5]. In time critical-applications [1, 6], such as safe robot navigation in dynamic smart factory environments, SDE detection should be performed continuously over voluminous streams of movement data arriving at high speeds. In such scenarios, extracting SDEs out of raw streams is a challenging task engaging (a) online neural network training for continuously maintaining an up-to-date model for SDE labelling purposes and (b) semantic-aware trajectory processing for identifying homogeneous movement portions, defining the SDE duration, before using the neural model for labelling it. By definition, output SDEs are simple pieces of information (Listing 2), but the volume and velocity of the original raw streams (Listing 1) in large scale smart factory applications call for scaling out (parallelizing) the computation to a number of machines to ensure real-time processing. Therefore, both (a) and (b) should be set up in state-of-the-art, relevant platforms [7, 9] to allow for direct deployment over computer clusters and/or the cloud. To tackle these challenges we develop SSTRESED, a prototype for scalable SDE detection over streaming movement data. For the first time, SSTRESED establishes a direct connection between semantic trajectory computation and SDE detection in the streaming context. This is in contrast to prior art [9, 10] which uses predetermined, application-defined time windows to a priori restrict eligible SDE durations.

2 The SSTRESED Prototype

SSTRESED (Figure 1) composes two connected pipelines distributed across worker machines running in the cloud. In the robotic scenario of Section 1, truthful, timestamped and labeled movement streams are continuously produced by robotic simulators, such as <https://github.com/rock-simulation>, as SDEs and their raw features, per robot (Listing 1).

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■ **Figure 1** SSTRESED Architecture. Training (blue) and SDE Detection (red) Pipelines.

■ **Listing 1** Example training stream for a single simulated robot. Unlabelled movement streams lack a SDE label (last column in the figure). Thousands of such streams can be ingested by SSTRESED in large scale applications.

time	...	pos_x	pos_y	pos_z	...	rot_w	SDE
8.35	...	-3.626	14.921	0.258	...	0.9951	stopped at Station1
30.57
41.15	...	-7.446	23.866	0.257	...	0.0977	moves to Station3
41.12	...	-7.444	23.867	0.258	...	0.0972	rotating

The training pipeline (blue-colored path in Figure 1) continuously receives these robot movement time series ingested in Apache Kafka partitions of the Training Topic. The Training Topic is read by parallel PyTorch Learners. Each such learner, utilizes an identical neural model (specified by the application), but performs the training process on a separate set of robots. The local models learned at each Learner i (top of Figure 1) are synchronized into a global neural model maintained by a Parameter Server [2]. At a global model update, new weights of the neural network are written to a Weights Topic of Kafka.

The SDE detection pipeline (red-colored path in Figure 1) receives raw, unlabeled streaming movement data, partitioned in the Movement Streams Kafka Topic. These incoming tuples, ingested directly from the application field, have the same schema as those of the Training Topic, but lack a label/SDE field. Ingested Movement Streams of robots (or, optionally, samples of them [8, 11]) are processed by a distributed version of SeTraStream [12] developed in Apache Flink. Distributed SeTraStream uses each parallel Segmentor i to continuously identify homogeneous movement portions based on the ingested features per robot, thus semantically and temporally segmenting each trajectory. In that, the duration of a SDE is determined, which also bounds the feature tensors that should then be used for labeling the SDE. Each parallel Segmentor i writes the result of its processing to an intermediate Kafka topic connecting Distributed SeTraStream with a PyTorch Semantic Tagger in the red-colored path. Each parallel Tagger i (bottom of Figure 1) of the Semantic Tagger, at any given time instance, reads the up-to-date weights from the Weights Topic and uses the updated neural model to label SDEs. The final SSTRESED output goes to the SDEs Kafka topic in the form of tuples as illustrated in Listing 2 (per robot).

■ **Listing 2** SSTRESED output SDE Stream for the movement of a single robot.

Time_from	Time_to	SDE
4.25	8.35	moving to Station2
8.35	8.36	stopped at Station2
...
39.00	41.15	rotating

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